

INFORMATION AND DIGITAL LITERACY: THEIR CONCEPTS AND SKILLS

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ABSTRACT

This article analyzes the concepts of information and digital literacy. Also, it shows how important to develop information literacy and digital literacy in our society in this growing information age. The examples of information and digital literacy skills are given. If somebody hopes to improve information literacy skills, they can try simple steps which are described in this scientific article. Also, they can find how to improve digital literacy skills according to four major principles of digital literacy that should be taken into account when you, your child or your students are learning and developing your digital literacy skills and using technology.

Keywords: information literacy, digital literacy, research skills, critical thinking skills, computer technology skills, communication skills.

АННОТАЦИЯ

В данной статье анализируются понятия информационная и цифровая грамотность. Кроме того, это показывает, насколько важно развивать информационную грамотность и цифровую грамотность в нашем обществе в этот растущий информационный век. Приведены примеры навыков информационной и цифровой грамотности. Если кто-то надеется улучшить навыки информационной грамотности, он может попробовать простые шаги, описанные в этой научной статье. Кроме того, они могут узнать, как улучшить навыки цифровой грамотности в соответствии с четырьмя основными принципами цифровой грамотности, которые следует учитывать, когда вы, ваш ребенок или ваши ученики изучаете и развиваете свои навыки цифровой грамотности и используете технологии.

Ключевые слова: информационная грамотность, цифровая грамотность, исследовательские навыки, навыки критического мышления, навыки работы с компьютерными технологиями, коммуникативные навыки.

INTRODUCTION

Our first President I.A.Karimov, foreseeing the prospects of independent Uzbekistan, mentioned: "The revival of spiritual values also means their adaptation to the values of the modern world and information civilization⁷". Information and digital literacy both play vital roles in our society and are necessary tools for citizens to have in this growing information age. "Student skill requirements are changed, you need not only to read, write and count, you need to be able to organize resources data, collaborate effectively, collect, evaluate and use information⁸". Thus, we can talk about the need for a modern person to have information literacy as an element of human culture and as an obligatory condition for a comfortable existence in society, and its formation turns out to be one of the most important tasks of the education system. "Information literacy is the ability to operate with any information, and the study new object on any material: from traditional - books, magazines, filing cabinets – to the most extraordinary technical innovations. Information literacy is the ability to formulate information need, request, seek, select, evaluate and interpret information in whatever form it is presented⁹". "Digital literacy is the ability to use information and communication technologies to find, evaluate, create, and communicate information, requiring both cognitive and technical skills. Digital Literacy is the ability and skill to find, evaluate, utilize, share, and create content using information technologies and the Internet. It differs from regular literacy that is offline and involves reading, writing, grammar and syntax [4]". Digital literacy leads to changes in the labor market, in educational standards, identification of needs in the formation of new competencies of the population and is focused on the reorganization of the educational process.

"Information literacy skills, which are sometimes referred to as media literacy or digital literacy skills, refer to your ability to identify, assess, organize, utilize and communicate information in any format. Though these skills are important in a wide range of situations, they are particularly valuable when evaluating the quality and credibility of a website, attributing credit to a source, acquiring new knowledge, solving a problem or making a decision, which is why they are essential for functioning effectively in the workplace¹⁰." Digital Literacy may be about a person's ability to read and write online or using technology such as computers, smartphones and Kindles, but it's also a lot more than that. With the impact of social media, Digital Literacy

⁷ Yugay, E. V. (2021). Digital culture and its influence on value aspects of human being. ISJ Theoretical & Applied Science, 12 (104), 422-425. Soi: <http://s-o-i.org/1.1/TAS-12-104-29> Doi: <https://dx.doi.org/10.15863/TAS.2021.12.104.29>

⁸ Кашина Е. А. Прогнозирование структуры интегрированного курса информатики: дис. ... канд.пед. наук. — Екатеринбург, 1997. — С. 187

⁹ https://ds22-ros.edu.yar.ru/informatsionnaya_gramotnost.pdf

¹⁰ <https://www.indeed.com/career-advice/career-development/information-literacy-skills>

skills also now includes a wide range of skills like uploading content on YouTube to sharing things on Facebook. “In order to accelerate the progress of digital technologies and create a favorable environment for their development, the main tasks of the digital development of the Republic of Uzbekistan are defined in the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On Approval of the Concept of the National Strategy “Digital Uzbekistan 2030¹¹”.

METHODS

The following examples of information and digital skills were chosen by the method of comparative and content analysis.

Examples of information literacy skills. Information literacy skills encompass and rely on a wide range of other skills, such as:

- Research skills. Research skills allow you to find the solution to an issue or answer to a question by gathering, analyzing and interpreting information about a specific topic. This process entails several other skills, including: problem-solving, time management, note-taking, attention to detail;
- Critical thinking skills. Critical thinking refers to your ability to evaluate facts so that you can fully understand a topic or issue and develop an effective solution. Objectivity is vital in creative thinking because it allows you to analyze a problem without allowing assumptions, emotions or biases to influence your judgment;
- Computer technology skills. Because information literacy often involves determining the validity of the information you find on websites and crediting online sources, basic computer skills are essential. The software skills necessary for information literacy allow you to use applications and programs efficiently and effectively;
- Communication skills. Communication skills are the abilities that enable you to receive and convey all kinds of information. There are several different types of communication, such as: written, verbal, nonverbal, visual.

Because you can communicate in so many different ways, this skill requires empathy, observation, writing, reading, speaking and active listening.

Examples of digital literacy skills. “Today, the role of digital culture in the formation of the spiritual and moral values of Uzbek youth is determined in the system of values that are necessary for:

- Using your phone to check emails;
- Using an online search engine to find the answer to a question;

¹¹ Yugay, E. 2021. Цифровая культура и общество: проблемы их взаимоотношений в условиях глобализации. Общество и инновации. 2, 7/5 (авг. 2021), 58–67. DOI:<https://doi.org/10.47689/2181-1415-vol2-iss7/S-pp58-67>.

- Using online search to complete a research project;
- Creating an online profile on a social media platform.

Children will learn digital literacy skills by using technology and this will help them to interact in this digital world around them. We also have a lot of resources on digital literacy that will help students with this exploration in a safe and supported way. This Digital literacy journey resource pack contains an entire week's worth of lessons to help children explore and understand different changes in digital technologies that are developing every day.

DISCUSSION

How to improve information literacy skills? If you're hoping to improve your information literacy skills, you can try following these simple steps:

1. Develop your ability to recognize quality sources. One of the most important aspects of information literacy is your ability to discern which sources are credible. To determine if a website is trustworthy, check the credentials of the author and the source, assess the sources that the author cites and examine the date that the piece was written. It can also be helpful to figure out if the publisher is reputable and check to see what kinds of reviews and endorsements the source has received.
2. Learn the intricacies of plagiarism. Information literacy is about finding and using quality information, so learning about copyright laws and plagiarism are key. Figure out the steps you should take to determine which content you can use and how to appropriately cite your sources.
3. Utilize advanced search techniques. You can use specific search strategies to make your online search results both more relevant and more accurate. This involves things like the proper use of keywords and using quality databases other than your basic search engine.
4. Practice your research skills. By regularly practicing your information literacy skills, you can develop your abilities in this area. Try taking on research projects at work and in your personal life.

How to improve digital literacy skills according to four major principles of digital literacy that should be taken into account when you, your child or your students are learning and developing your digital literacy skills and using technology. These principles are as follows:

1. Comprehension - Students first must reach a level of comprehension of digital literacy through lessons, home practice and support group work. This will help children grasp basic concepts of safety and digital literacy that will form the foundation of their learning;

2. Interdependence - The next principle that children will learn is interdependence. This is the concept that different digital platforms are dependent on each other. Students will learn that all forms of digital media are connected to another. This can also help them understand data protection as, due to the sheer abundance of media, it is necessary that media forms not simply co-exist, but supplement one another;
3. Social Factors - It is important that children understand that there are social influences and factors in having an online digital presence. Sharing information, content, media and stories through a certain digital platform can determine the success of that media;
4. Curation - The final principle that students will learn about is curating their own content and digital information. An easy way to do this is through using platforms that offer the ability to store and save content for later. Sites with a focus on this such as Pinterest.com allow students to save content and ideas on their own platforms whilst sharing minimal personal data.

CONCLUSION

Thus, a large project that influenced the development of digital skills in Uzbekistan was the creation of an IT technology park as part of the resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers “On measures to create a technology park for software products and information technologies” dated January 10, 2019. The successful experience of the IT park created in the capital has become an example for scaling up in other regions of the Republic. “Our state already today sees the need for the development of digital literacy in the field of education and management. On a national scale, there is a shortage of personnel in the field of digital technologies, and therefore there is an increasing need to create a matrix educational environment, where universities (both public and corporate) should become an experimental platform for various forms of education using advanced technologies and taking into account the specifics digital culture of youth¹²”.

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¹² Yugay, E. 2021. Цифровая культура и общество: проблемы их взаимоотношений в условиях глобализации. *Общество и инновации*. 2, 7/5 (авг. 2021), 58–67. DOI:<https://doi.org/10.47689/2181-1415-vol2-iss7/S-pp58-67>.

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